

INTERACTIVE METHOD "ADVANTAGES OF SWOT ANALYSIS"

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Abstract. This article highlights the benefits of the SWOT analysis method, which is one of the interactive methods used to improve the quality of education, for students and the main tasks of this method.

Key words: education, method, analysis, pedagogues, students, school.

Nowadays, a lot of attention is paid to the quality of education of students and at the same time, to what extent they can apply it. Determining the priorities for the systematic reform of general secondary and extracurricular education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the moral, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, education in order to introduce innovative forms and methods of education into the process, as well as the PF- According to Decree No. 5538:

The following are defined:

a) The concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 (hereinafter referred to as the Concept) should be approved in accordance with Appendix 1 and the following should be provided in it: PISA (The Program for International Students) of the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030 Assessment) To reach the top 30 advanced countries of the world according to the rating of the student assessment program at the international level;

updating the content of the continuing education system in terms of quality, as well as training, retraining and upgrading professional personnel;

improvement of the teaching methodology, step-by-step implementation of the principles of individualization in the educational process;

introduction of modern information and communication technologies and innovative projects in the field of public education;[1]

To bring the quality of education to international level and at the same time students should be well understood to be able to apply the information without blindly memorizing it. For this, we need to use interactive methods, which will help students to better acquire the knowledge taught. When choosing interactive methods of teaching, the purpose of education, the number and opportunities of students, the educational and material conditions of the

educational institution, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. are taken into account. Modern teaching methods are widely used in the education process.

The use of modern teaching methods leads to high efficiency in the teaching process. It is appropriate to choose these methods based on the didactic task of each lesson. While preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with various methods that activate the activities of the students leads to an increase in the level of learning of the students. - in the discussion, it is a decision with consensus. The advantage of this method is that the entire activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares him for an independent life.

"The great goal of education is not to impart knowledge, but to teach behavior"

G. Spencer

Educational methods serve to illuminate the purpose of education, with the help of which the ways of mastering the content of education are expressed, the interaction of teachers and students and their characteristics are reflected. Interactive learning methods encourage students to be active, compare and contrast what they have mastered, and effectively affect the precise mastery of concepts within a given topic. One such influential method is the SWOT analysis method. If we look at the history of the origin of this method, it is said that it belongs to the professors of Harvard University, while some say that Sea Roland Christensen created the basis of the theory in the 1950s. The acronym SWOT was first used at Harvard in 1963 by Professor Kenneth Andrews at a conference devoted to the content of business policy. In 1965, SWOT analysis was proposed to develop a firm's behavioral strategy.

Structure of SWOT abbreviation:

S-strongs - strengths.

W - weakness

O-opportunity

T - threats - obstacles.

Initially, this analysis was developed for business development, and it gave managers of different levels the opportunity to quickly implement, analyze, and compare changes in business processes based on the main goals of the company. SWOT analysis helps to create a structured description of a particular situation, conclusions can be drawn based on this description. Analysis – is a logical way of knowing, which is to mentally break down an object (phenomenon, process) into parts, elements or signs, to compare them and to study them sequentially in

order to identify important or specific qualities and characteristics. This allows us to make correct and reasonable decisions. This analysis is a primary assessment method based on a four-pronged review of the situation. To date, this method has covered many areas. In particular, this method can be effectively used in the field of education and applied to many lessons.[2]

Through the method of SWOT analysis, we help the expansion of students' thinking and their cognitive development. We teach them to think comprehensively and then draw conclusions, to have their own independent opinions.

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